

THE EFFECT OF GAS TEXTURING TECHNOLOGY ON THE TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF UNIDIRECTIONAL (UD) CARBON FIBRE (CF) REINFORCED POLYAMIDE-12(PA-12) COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

Unidirectional (UD) carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics have high specific strength and stiffness, but they fail in a brittle manner with little warning when subjected to uniaxial tension. This inherent brittleness limits the application of such composites, especially in load-controlled scenarios.

Because the tensile strength and stiffness of UD composites varies as the orientation of the fibre is changed [1], introducing a small degree fibre misalignment could potentially increase the non-linearity in its strain-stress response without severely reducing the tensile stiffness. Previous reports show that the tensile strength and modulus of UD composites decreased as the fibre alignment angle increased [2]. In 1989, Manders et al. found that misalignment of the prepreg by $\pm 1^\circ$ during the lay-up process caused 28% reduction in tensile strength in the fibre direction [2]. Khatibzadeh found that the notched tensile strength was also decreased as fibre angle increased. [3,4]. However, there has been little investigation on the tensile performance with randomly-distributed small angle misalignment. Considering the uniaxial tension load case, the purpose of introducing this randomly-distributed fibre misalignment is to allow that part of the composite with perfect fibre alignment to fail first but with sufficient undamaged misaligned fibre remaining to carry the load. Such a composite would fail in steps rather than in a catastrophic manner.

In 1990s, gas-texturing technology was applied in manufacturing commingled reinforcement fibre yarn and thermoplastic polymer matrix fibre yarn to form a hybrid roving, which was then manufactured into continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic polymers by the pultrusion process [5]. One of the advantages of this technology is that it can shorten the polymer melt flow path between the reinforcement filaments, so it allows the manufacturing process to be less time-consuming than film stacking technology. More importantly, it improved uniformity of reinforcement distribution in polymer matrix. [6]. However, Lauke et al. found that the longitudinal tensile strength of UD glass fibre reinforced polyamide made using gas-texturing technology was lower than its predicted value obtained via the rule of mixtures. They claimed that this reduction was caused by the misalignment of the reinforcement, but there was little investigation of the misalignment degree of the reinforcement in this literature [7].

Because the tensile properties [2-4] and compressive properties [8] of continuous UD composite are influenced by as little as a 1° fibre alignment angle change, methods of accurately measuring fibre alignment in composites has been investigated since 1980s. Two of the most popular methods for measuring fibre misalignment are Yurgartis's method and multi-field image analysis [9,10]. Yurgartis used the fact that the fibre with a circular cross section will show ellipsoid when cut an angle other than 90° to the fibre direction. Through

measuring the major and minor axial dimensions of the ellipsoid, the individual fibre alignment angle was obtained. The accuracy of this method was $\pm 0.25^\circ$ [9]. In 2001, Creighton designed a multi-field image analysis to measure fibre misalignment in a low magnification microscopy image. Due to the low magnification of image, the fibres in the longitudinal section of the composite were treated as lines via a computer-aid image recognizing program. Then the angle between the individual fibre line and the normalized fibre direction was obtained. This method is less time-consuming and more effective in measuring the fibre misalignment in a large domain than the former method, but the results obtained were less reliable as the size of the domain was decreased [10]. Due to the limited thickness (0.09 ± 0.01 mm) of the available composite tape, the former method was selected in this study.

In the present work, a gas-texturing device was used to combine two carbon fibre tows together and to also introduce a small degree of misalignment into the combined fibre tow. A single-fibre tensile test was used to determine the effect of gas texturing on the fibre tensile properties. Carbon fibre reinforced PA-12 tape was manufactured using a powder wet-impregnation method [11]. The distribution of fibre alignment in the composite tape produced was quantified based on Yurgartis's method [9], and the tensile performance of the composite was investigated.

2 Experiment

2.1 Materials

Continuous IM7 tows (HexTow®-12K, Hexcel Co., Cambridge, UK), PA-12 powder (Vestosint®-2159, supplied by Evonik Degussa GmbH, Weiterstadt, Germany) and N₂ (BOC UK Co. London, UK) were used.

2.2 Manufacture route

Fig. 1 shows the design of the gas-texturing device. Two fibre tows pass over a PTFE perforated bar. A N₂ (pressure=2.5 bar) flow passing through small holes (diameter 1mm) in the bar causes the fibre

tows to spread into filaments or small bundles, with some degree of misalignment.

The resulting combined fibre tow was used to produce a CF/PA-12 (fibre volume fraction = $60 \pm 2\%$) composite tape with thickness of 0.09 ± 0.01 mm and width of 8 ± 1 mm. Fig. 2 shows the setup of manufacturing route. Details can also be found in [11]. The fibre tow was passed through a 2L polymer suspension bath that used 13 pins to spread the fibres and help the fibre tow pick up the thermoplastic powder. Next drying and melting intra-red heating stages were used to evaporate the water carried by the fibre tow and then melt the polymer powder. Finally, the heated shear pins were used to further spread and consolidate the melt-impregnated fibre tow into a composite tape with a smooth surface. A two-belt puller was used to control the speed of manufacturing process at 0.5 m/min. In order to keep the fibre volume fraction in the composite tape at 60 %, a concentrated polymer suspension was added into the bath during the manufacturing process at intervals.

2.2 Tensile test on as-received and gas-textured CF

A Linkam TST350 tensile stress tester (Linkam Scientific Instrument Ltd, Surrey, UK) with 20N load cell was used to measure the tensile strength and the apparent modulus of as-received and gas-textured CF according to ISO 11566 standard [12]. 25 fibre filaments from each group were tested on a gauge length of 25mm at 15 μ m/s. The test setup is as seen in Fig. 3. In order to evaluate the variation and distribution of fibre strength, the cumulative failure probability $P_{R,i}$ of the i th fibre was calculated through equation (1). The Weibull-modulus m of fibre strength is given by the slope of the $\ln[-\ln(1-P_{R,i})]$ vs $\ln\sigma_i$ plot, as seen in equation (2) [13].

$$P_{R,i} = \frac{R_i}{N+1} \quad (1)$$

$$\ln[-\ln(1 - P_R)] = m \ln \sigma + Constant \quad (2)$$

Where R_i is the rank of i th fibre, N is the total number of tested fibres and σ_i is i th fibre strength.

2.3 Tensile test on CF/PA-12 composite

The composite tape was cut into 200 mm lengths and end tabbed with woven glass fabric/polyester composite (thickness =1.5 mm). The free gauge length was 100 mm. Five specimens were tested under uniaxial tensile load (Instron 4566, Instron Ltd, Bucks, UK) at a crosshead rate of 1 mm/min. Digital image correlation (ARAMI-2M, GOM UK Ltd, Coventry, UK) was used to record the strain over the whole gauge length. The set up is as seen in Fig. 4.

2.4 Quantification of misalignment in UD composite

After tensile testing, the samples were cut from the end-tab region at an angle of 5° to the nominal fibre direction (Fig. 5 (a)). Twenty microscopy images (50x magnification) were taken along one edge of each cut sample. A typical image is shown in Fig. 5 (b). By measuring the major and minor axial dimensions of the cut fibre surfaces, the fibre angle can be determined, as given in equation (3) [9]. For each image, 10 fibres were randomly selected for measurement. For selected regions, all the fibres shown in one image were measured.

$$\theta = \sin^{-1} \frac{d}{l} \quad (3)$$

Where θ is cut fibre angle, l and d are the major and minor axial dimensions of the cut fibre surfaces respectively.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Effect of gas texturing on the tensile properties of CF

The plots of tensile cumulative failure probability P_R vs fibre strength σ of as-received and gas-textured fibres fit well with the Weibull probability distribution in Fig. 6 (a). As seen in Table 1, the tensile strength of the gas-textured CF was 15% lower than that of as-received fibre. The possible reason for this was that the high-pressure gas (2.5

bars) introduced flaws or damage onto the fibre surface. Erden et al. similarly found that the CF strength after high-pressure (2.5 bars) plasma oxidation gas treatment was decreased by 17% [14]. In Fig. 6 (b), the Weibull modulus of as-received CF was 22% larger than that of gas-textured CF, which means that the scatter in the former was less than that in the latter. It is possibly due to the fact that this treatment did not evenly damage CF surface in 24K filaments within two fibre tows during the continuous manufacturing process. However, tensile modulus did not significantly change after gas-texturing treatment, which means that the treatment did not change the internal structure of CF. The strain to failure of gas-textured CF was decreased by 15%, which was the same as the reduction in CF strength as seen in Table. 1. Also the linear stress-strain response to failure is given.

3.2 Effect of gas texturing on the fibre alignment in composite tape

Fig. 7 shows the typical fibre angle distributions in (a) non-gas-textured and (b) gas-textured CF/PA-12 composite tapes. The variation of fibre angle in non gas-textured CF/PA-12 composite is less than that of composite without treatment. About 90% untreated fibres in CF/PA-12 only have less than $\pm 1^\circ$ misalignment, while the fibres in gas-textured CF/PA-12 were misaligned by $\pm 2.25^\circ$. This means that gas texturing increased the fibre misalignment in the UD composite within the composite tape. Furthermore, fibre misalignment in some local region is larger than others even in the same sample, as seen in Fig. 9.

3.3 Effect of gas texturing on the tensile behavior of composite tape

As mentioned in section 3.1 and 3.2, gas-texturing decreased the tensile strength and strain to failure of the fibres and introduced randomly distributed small angle misalignment into UD CF/PA-12 composite. The combination of these two effects caused a significant change in the tensile stress-strain behavior of the composite (Fig. 9). The composite using the gas-textured fibre failed in steps rather than a catastrophic fracture. As seen in Fig. 10 and

Fig. 11, part of the gas-textured CF/PA-12 still carried some load after the first failure occurred, while the non gas-textured CF/PA-12 completely failed in a catastrophic manner. The difference in failure mode could be associated with the difference in fibre alignment of the two composites. The straight fibres will carry the greater stress and so are more likely to fail first. Of the remaining fibres those with least misalignment will fail next and so the failure process can be more gradual in the gas-textured composite with its larger range of fibre misalignment.

4 Conclusions

A gas-texturing technology was developed to introduce small angle misalignment of fibre into UD CF/PA-12 composite. Gas-texturing treatment decreased CF tensile strength and strain to failure without significant change in tensile modulus. Due to the combined effect of degradation in CF tensile strength and small angle misalignment, the composite fails in steps rather than in a single catastrophic fracture when subjected to tension in the nominal fibre direction.

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Fig. 1. Design of gas-texturing device (a) photo (b) schematic diagram

Fig. 2. Setup of manufacture route of UD CF/PA-12 composite tape

Fig. 3. Setup of single-fibre tensile test

Fig. 4. Setup of tensile test on UD composite

Fig. 5. (a) Schematic diagram of microscopy sample preparation (b) Typical microscopy image of polished sample surface

Fig. 6. (a) The cumulative failure curve and (b) Weibull plots of as-received and gas-textured CF strength

Table. 1. Tensile properties of as-received and gas-textured fibre

	Strength (MPa)	Strain to failure (%)	Modulus (GPa)	Weibull modulus of strength
As-received	4843 ±192	1.72±0.07	273.7±2.5	5.34
Gas-textured	4152±201	1.48±0.08	267.4±4.2	4.37

Fig. 7. Typical untransformed fibre angle distribution in (a) non- and (b) gas textured CF/PA-12 composite prepreg

Fig. 8. Two microscopy images taken from the same polished sample (gas-textured CF/PA-12 composite) surface

Fig. 9. Tensile stress-strain curves of (a) non gas-textured and (b) gas-textured CF/PA-12

Fig. 10. Images of gas-textured CF/PA-12 tensile specimen (a) before the testing (b) after the first failure (c) after the final failure

Fig. 11. Images of no gas-textured CF/PA-12 tensile specimen (a) before the testing (b) after the final failure

Table. 2. Tensile properties of no gas textured and gas-textured CF/PA-12

	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Failure strain (%)	
			First	Final
No gas-textured	2495±105	165.9±9.7	1.61±0.03	
Gas-textured	2313±116	164.9±7.4	1.37±0.07	1.58±0.09

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